

FIELD OF SPECIALIZATION PREFERENCES AND STUDENTS' PERFORMANCE IN TLE 9

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ABSTRACT

This study sought to find out the relationship between the “Field of Specialization Preferences and Students’ Performance in TLE 9” among the one hundred twenty grade 9 students of Bondoc Peninsula Agricultural High School. A descriptive research design was used in the study using self-survey questionnaires which were administered through google forms. The statistical tools used were the frequency distribution, mean, percentage and Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient or Spearman Rho (rs) were used to measure the relationship of paired ranks – field of specialization preferences and students’ performance in TLE. The findings of the study reveal that majority of the respondents were 15 years old having sixty (60) or 50% of the respondents, 95 or 79% were female; the field of specialization choices, majority of the respondents chose food processing as their first choice of specialization which consists of 26 or 22% of the respondents, while 28 or 23% of the respondents chose cookery as their second choice of specialization. Most of their parents were high school graduates earning Php. 5,000.00 and below monthly family income. The respondents' perception towards their interest and attitudes were both Agree with an overall mean of 4.22 and 3.96 respectively. With regards to the level of awareness on the needs of the community, finding shows that the overall mean is 3.97(Agree), While on the level of Capability of the School as to Facilities and equipment in terms of Laboratory Facilities and tools and equipment were both Agree with an overall mean of 4.01 and 3.95 respectively, as to Teachers’ Competence in terms of Teaching Strategies with an overall mean of 4.14, Classroom Management with an overall mean of 4.17 and the Instructional materials has an overall mean of 4.09. Based from the result, the students’ performance in achievement test is fifty-two (52) or 43.44% ranges to 85-89 rating (Very Good) sixty three (63) or 52.50% ranges above 89 rating and interpreted as Excellent in their cumulative skill, in terms of work ethics fifty six (56) or 46.67% of the respondents range of above 89 and interpreted as excellent. As to a product, it can be noticed that sixty-seven (67) or 55.83% of the respondents were in the range of 85-89 (Very Good). The students’ performance as to 2nd quarter grade, manipulative skills, work ethics and product are not significantly related to the students’ variables in terms of attitudes and interest when tested at $^{**}(.01)$ and $^{*}(.05)$. The Students’ Performance in terms of 2nd quarter grade, manipulative skills, work ethics and product are not significantly related to the community needs, schools’ facilities, instructional materials, and teaching strategies when tested at $^{*}(.05)$. On the contrary the students’ performance in terms of product is significantly related to the tools and equipment ($r=0.186$) and classroom management (0.209). The

hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the perceived interest and attitudes and performance of the students in TLE 9 is therefore supported. The hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the students' performances and community needs and capability of the school is therefore partially supported.

Keywords: Specialization choices, Community Needs, School Capability, Teachers' Competence, Students' Performance